

PETROLOGY AND GEOCHEMISTRY OF LUNAR FELDSPATHIC BRECCIA METEORITE BECHAR 003: IMPLICATIONS OF THE GENESIS OF KREEP-FREE/POOR MG-SUITE

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Introduction: The lunar highlands Mg-suite rocks, including dunite, troctolite, anorthosite, norite, and related lithologies, represent key samples for investigating magmatic processes on the Moon [1], bridge the crystallization of the lunar magma ocean (LMO) and the development of secondary lunar crust. Traditional interpretations based on Apollo samples suggest that their origin is closely associated with KREEP-rich components and that their distribution is largely restricted to the Procellarum KREEP Terrane (PKT) [2-5]. However, in recent years, a number of lithic clasts exhibiting mineralogical characteristics of the Mg-suite but showing geochemically KREEP-free/poor signature have been progressively identified in lunar meteorites and some returned samples [3, 6-7]. The composition of the mantle source, the role of KREEP, the global distribution of Mg-suite rocks, and the factors controlling their magmatic evolution continue to be major unresolved issues in lunar science.

Lunar meteorite Bechar 003 is a feldspathic breccia whose matrix contains abundant mineral fragments and lithic clasts of various types (Fig.1). This study conducted the comprehensive and systematic analysis of the petrological, mineralogical and geochemical characteristics of Bechar 003 to provide new perspectives on the formation of lunar KREEP-free/poor Mg-Suite and evolution of the lunar highlands.

Fig 1. BSE images of Bechar 003 lunar meteorite (a: Meteorite Thin Section; b: Meteorite Target)

Methods: This study combined multiple in-situ analysis techniques at the State Key Laboratory of Geological Processes and Mineral Resources, China University of Geosciences (GPMR-CUG), including FEI field-emission scanning electron microscope (FEG-SEM) equipped with EBSD (HKL) and EDS (Oxford Instruments Analytical Ltd.), the TESCAN Integrated Mineral Analyzer system (TIMA3

XGHM), the JEOL JXA-8230 electron microprobe analyzer (EPMA), the automated confocal micro-Raman spectrometer (XploRA Plus) and laser ablation inductively coupled with plasma mass spectrometry (LA-ICP-MS).

Petrography and Mineral Chemistry: The types of clasts in Bechar 003 are mainly feldspathic clasts (including anorthositic clasts, anorthositic gabbro clasts, gabbroic anorthositic clasts, and troctolitic anorthosite clasts; using the classification criteria of -D. Stöffler et al. 1980 [8]), along with impact melt breccia clasts (including impact melt breccia clasts containing clasts and crystalline impact melt). The silicate minerals (i.e., pyroxene, olivine, and plagioclase) are the main phases, while the non-silicate minerals (e.g., chromite, metallic iron, Fe-Ni metal, silica and troilite) are less common that mostly occurring within grains or in intergranular spaces in Bechar 003. The matrix of the meteorite is relatively large-grained and consists mostly of individual mineral fragments. Exsolution lamellae are observed in the high-Ca pyroxene grains, olivine-pyroxene grains and sulfide-pyroxene grains associations are common in the matrix of the meteorite.

The plagioclase grains in Bechar 003 are mainly calcium plagioclase grains. They show similar compositional ranges of An# from 94 to 99, which is a typical characteristic of the lunar highland rocks. No maskelynite was observed in anorthositic gabbro clasts using the Raman spectrometer. Pyroxene grains are mainly composed of fine-grained pigeonite and augite, the exsolution makes their compositions more complex, usually have wide ranges of variations ($\text{En}_{40.7-71.2}\text{Wo}_{3.0-42.7}$). Unlike pyroxene grains, olivine grains have smaller ranges of compositional variations (Fo_{64-82}).

Anorthositic clasts have relatively high Mg# values of 62.1–75.2, so we identified them as lunar magnesian anorthositic clasts (MAN). The graph of anorthositic gabbro clasts plotting the relationship between Mg# values in mafic minerals and the value of An in plagioclase grains shows the plotted points at fields of FAN, Mg-Suite, and between them, the graph Eu/Sm values and Sm shows the plotted points at fields of Mg-Suite. We identified anorthositic gabbro clasts as KREEP-free/poor Mg-Suite.

Rare Earth Element Compositions of Plagioclase: The REE patterns of plagioclase in anorthositic clasts and gabbro anorthositic clasts are within the range of plagioclase REE compositions reported from lunar anorthositic meteorites and Apollo FANs.

But the plagioclase in anorthositic gabbro clasts is slightly lower than lunar meteorites and Apollo Mg-suite rocks (Fig.3a, b).

Equilibrium Liquid Compositions: We back-calculated the REE compositions of liquids in equilibrium with this mineral to evaluate the partial melt compositions of the clasts analyzed here. Liquids in equilibrium with plagioclase grains from anorthositic gabbro clasts have relatively flat chondrite-normalized REE patterns, some with small negative Eu anomalies.

The Petrogenesis of KREEP-Free/Poor Mg-suite: We performed trace-element partitioning behaviors of the KREEP-free lunar primary mantle source (LPUM) during partial melting and fractional crystallization for the Bechar 003 lunar meteorite. The results indicate that the KREEP-free/poor Mg-suite clasts could have been generated from the KREEP-free/poor lunar mantle source (LPUM) through low degree of partial melting, followed by high degree of fractional crystallization (Fig.3c). KREEP is not necessarily required for the generation of Mg-suite parental magmas [7,9].

Fig 3. (a, b) CI chondrite normalized REE concentrations and pattern of plagioclase, (c) Trace-element partitioning behaviors of the KREEP-free lunar primary mantle source (LPUM) during partial melting and fractional crystallization.

Discussion: Previous studies have suggested that MAN clasts represent distinct lithology related to the lunar Mg-suite, may constitute an important component of the farside crust and could be more representative of the pristine lunar highlands than Apollo samples [10-11]. Combined with remote sensing observations and lunar meteorite studies, these data suggest that primitive feldspathic crust may be dominated by ferroan anorthosites (FANs) on the nearside and magnesian anorthosites (MANs) on the farside, likely reflecting asymmetric crystallization of the primordial lunar magma ocean [10-12].

A systematic comparative study of the Bechar 003 lunar meteorite and samples returned by the Chang'e-6 mission from the South Pole-Aitken (SPA) basin on the lunar farside provides critical evidence for the coexistence of both KREEP-rich and KREEP-poor Mg-rich parental magma sources in the early Moon. During the late stage of the lunar magma ocean, mantle overturn driven by gravitational instabilities not only transported KREEP-free lower mantle materials toward shallower regions but also triggered extensive partial melting, which can plausibly explain the global distribution of KREEP-poor Mg-suite rocks.

Conclusion: Bechar 003 is a special lunar meteorite sample that contains both magnesian anorthositic clasts and KREEP-free/poor Mg-suite clasts. Their petrological, mineralogical and geochemical characteristics provide important clues regarding the distribution characteristics of KREEP components and the origin of the rock types in the lunar highlands. This investigation thus provides new constraints for understanding early lunar magmatic processes, source heterogeneity and the asymmetric magmatic evolution of the lunar nearside and farside.

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References: [1] Joy, K. H., & Arai, T. (2013) *Astronomy & Geophysics*, 54(4), 4.28-24.32. [2] Elardo, S.M. et al., (2012) *GCA*, 87, 154-177. [3] Shearer, C. K. et al., (2015) *AM*, 100(1), 294-325. [4] Elardo, S.M. et al., (2020) *NG*, 13(5), 339-343. [5] K. H. Joy et al. (2014) *GCA*, 144, 299-325. [6] Wang, Z. et al., (2025) *CEE*, 6(1), 170. [7] J. Gross et al. (2020) *JGR-P*, 125(5). [8] D. Stöffler et al. (1980) *Proc. Conf. Lunar Highlands Crust*, 51-70. [9] Prissel, T. C., & Gross, J. (2020). *EPSL*, 551, 116531. [10] Arai, T., et al., (2012) *Earth, Planets and Space*, 60(4), 433-444. [11] J. Gross et al. (2014) *EPSL*, 388, 318-328. [12] Ohtake, M. et al. (2014) *NG*, 5(6), 384-388.